

Abstract

Vertigo, split brains and organismal development. All very interesting phenomena holding secrets about consciousness. This is explored here.

The peculiarity in vertigo, split brains and organismal development

M. Ljubičić (Amenoum)

108. brigade ZNG 43, 35252 Sibirj, Croatia mljubic99@gmail.com

November 9, 2023

1 The peculiarity in vertigo, split brains and organismal development

Vertigo is an very interesting phenomenon. It is the evidence that we don't see the world directly through our eyes but it can also reveal secrets about consciousness. Our eyes are simply devices, much like digital cameras, which detected light convert to electrical signals. The signals from both eyes are integrated and stored in a buffer. This data is then, in the form of a hologram or a hallucination, interpreted as the view of the world, by our consciousness. Vertigo commonly occurs with the loss of blood pressure in the brain, which in extreme cases leads to loss of consciousness. Vertigo is commonly associated with crystals and fluids in the inner ear which provides us with means to sense movement and rotation. As the head moves/rotates the crystals and fluids move as well. This movement should stop when the head stops moving. But sometimes the crystals break away from the organs they're usually contained in.

This could be correlated with low blood pressure. Certain blood pressure may be required to ensure confinement of crystals.

In that case, they will continue spinning for a while even when the head stops. The brain thus receives the signal that the head is moving even though other signals (eg. those coming from the eyes) tell otherwise. This confusion is then manifested as symptoms of vertigo (eg. spinning hallucination, nausea, ..). But why does the brain override information coming from the eyes and create an illusion of spinning? Or does it? Perhaps the spinning is the result of spinning of consciousness. The brain might create the illusion to tell us that something

is wrong with the inner ear, but that seems odd and isn't nausea enough for that? If the brain really is creating the illusion why it doesn't do so in other cases? For example, why doesn't it *shake* the image when we're feeling cold? Why doesn't it create a hallucination of fire when we're about to have a fever? There are numerous examples where this could be useful and yet the brain just doesn't do that.

Some would even find it *cool*. Imagine your brain showing your heart rate in the corner of the image once that rate goes to extremes. No need for cyborgs..

Instead, the brain simply prefers the symptom in the form of some kind of pain. Therefore, it is very unlikely that the brain is creating the illusion of spinning in vertigo. So if the hallucination is not spinning, it must be the consciousness spinning. With consciousness decoupled from hallucination, this then becomes the evidence for the existence of the soul. Per my theories, the soul has an angular momentum by default (which, along with inclination, probably remains fixed during the time it is coupled with the body), it needs the information coming from the inner ear to maintain coherence and correlation of experience with the movement of the physical body.

2 Split brains

There's evidence for the existence of souls in split brains. In conventional theories consciousness is emergent and splitting the brain in two should split the consciousness as well. But studies show this is not the case, even after splitting, there remains a single conscious perceiver[1].

3 Organismal development

DNA contains recipes to build small parts of organisms (ie. proteins), but it does not contain blueprints of complete organs or organisms. Conventionally, it is assumed that somehow the spontaneous (emergent) self-organization leads to organs and then to the complete organism. Just like it was believed that consciousness emerges from self-organization of neurons in a neural network. But that's obviously not the case. Some form of blueprints does exist, it's just not in DNA. The blueprints probably exist as hallucinations toward which local reality has a tendency to converge with time. One can think of hallucinations as correlated (entangled) with interconnected entities (such as neurons, but entities don't have to be physically connected). This entanglement can be weak or strong. The entities affect the hallucination but the hallucination affects the entities as well. The influence is generally asymmetric, in case of organismal

development, the influence of hallucination on entities may dominate. There probably exists some kind of positive feedback, therefore, increasing the probability for a system to reach a particular eigenstate. As the singular consciousness in split brains suggests, there is no absolute emergence (one can, however, speak of relative emergence) or absolute causality, the two components of organismal development (cells/DNA and guiding hallucinations) are present relatively simultaneously. Even the, so called, spontaneous self-organization, eg. in a flock of birds, probably involves the hallucination, but here the influence of an individual on it could dominate (or, the entanglement is weak). In either case, emergence is relative. In the latter, one could say the hallucination emerged from the spontaneous self-organization, in the former, it's probably more appropriate to say that the organization emerged from hallucination. The hallucinations thus evolve and are correlated with consciousness. One could say there are different species of hallucinations. The self-organized flock of birds dissolves quickly because the hallucination did not (or could not) evolve further in that particular environment - the environment to which the individual is more adapted acting as an independent life-form rather than as part of a whole (it is generally much more likely to survive on its own with a complete set of roles rather than being a part of a whole where each individual may be more specialized and have a different role). A living organism is thus a dual entity - a physical body coupled to a mental component or a soul (which is also physical at some scale) providing guidance in development. One can assume that hallucinations have a peak some time during embryonic development, while at adult stage they effectively stop evolving, are weakly entangled with body components and occur more often as symptoms (eg. in dreams) of certain physiological states, although they still can act a guidance (as proven in g-tummo meditation[2]).

References

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